

**BEST PRACTICES OF PROMOTING A POSITIVE SCHOOL
LEARNING CLIMATE AMONG HEADTEACHERS
OF HIGH PERFORMING PRIMARY SCHOOLS AND EDUCATION -
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Abstract:

The study aims to examine the best practices of Promoting Positive School Learning Climate among Headteachers of High Performing Primary Schools in Malaysia according to headteachers' and teachers' perceptions. The Instructional Management Rating Scale modified by Hallinger and Heck (1996), Latip (2010), and, Surayya (2016) were used as the data collection instrument through survey questionnaire. There were 420 respondents of headteachers and teachers of various genders, ethnicity, type of schools, and, position of responsibilities at schools were participated. The result of the study demonstrated that the best practice was on dimension 'Developing and Enforcing Academic Standards' mean 4.4754. The second highest was on dimension 'Providing Incentives for Learning' mean 4.3729. Third and Fourth were dimensions 'Promoting Professional Development' and 'Providing Incentives for Teachers' with mean 4.3049 and 4.2500 respectively. It is hoped that this study will provide useful findings which will effectively assist the process of promoting a positive school learning climate by school leaders and teachers of primary and secondary schools. The study was expected provide significant results that may effectively contribute in the process of promoting a positive school learning climate among headteachers and teachers of primary and secondary schools world-wide. Consequently, facilitate and improve students' academic performance in achieving the first class human capital compatibly excellent nationally and internationally as stipulated in National Philosophy of Education, Vision 2020 and aspiration of the Education Development Plan 2013-2025 Malaysia.

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1. Introduction

The improvement of teaching and learning is strongly related to the school leader who has many roles and responsibilities as an instructional leader. Leadership in instructional matters should emerge freely from both the headteacher and teachers. Teachers deliver the instruction in the classroom. The headteacher is responsible for developing a school climate that is conducive to providing the very best instructional practices. It is the headteacher who should forge a partnership with teachers with the primary goal of improving teaching and learning. The headteacher is required to be a professional leader who takes appropriate action who is always in the school surroundings, enforce academic standards, and, consistently focuses on teaching and learning processes with accredited feedback.

2. Role of Headteacher at Primary Schools

Nowadays, the headteacher's roles are more complex because they are always linked with change. The role is very complex because the change which will be applied is various and difficult. Tajasom, and Zainal (2011) perceived that the role of the school leader, in models in the future, will be to encourage collaborative groupings of teachers to play a more central role in the instructional leadership of the school. This, however, will require the active participation of the school leader to facilitate change by motivating the staff and students, by reaching out to the community, and by continually improving the school. The assumption inherent, here, is that effective leaders manage and lead (Okorji, Igbokwe, & Ezeugbor (2016).

Hallinger and Heck (1996), Latif (2010) and Surayya (2016) suggest in their studies is that among the major instructional roles of headteacher are 'Developing and Enforcing Academic Standards', 'Providing Incentives for Teachers', 'Providing Incentives for Learning' and 'Promoting Professional Development' as stipulated in the Model of Instructional Leadership. These dimensions are discussed in the sections below.

2.1 Developing and Enforcing Academic Standards'

Clearly defined, high standards reinforce the high expectations necessary for improving student learning. One study that compares successful and less successful schools found that successful schools tended to require mastery of a defined set of skills prior to entry into the following grade. High standards are also promoted when increasing numbers of students are expected to master basic skills (Hallinger & Murphy, 1985).

Allen, Grigsby & Peters (2015) noted that principals must be able to recognize whether lessons are aligned with standards, develop classroom assessments consistent with standards, and evaluate student work for evidence that standards have been

achieved. Their knowledge should be deep enough to let them coach teachers using explanations, practical examples, and demonstration lessons. Just as important, leaders must demonstrate the same learning traits that they expect in teachers: openness to new ideas, willingness to be driven by results, and persistence in the face of difficulty.

Establishing a climate that promotes academic press has many benefits to the teaching and learning process. Chrispeels (1992, as cited in Alig-Mielcarek, 2003) noted that a qualitative study of eight elementary schools indicated that schools which focus the climate around high expectations, high achievable standards, and an orderly, serious environment, have a positive impact on teacher instruction. Teachers who work in a school with high academic press are more likely to use a variety of instructional strategies, plan diverse lessons to attend to different learning styles, monitor and provide feedback on student progress more frequently, collaborate with colleagues, demonstrate collegial behaviour, and attend to their own professional learning.

Those actions are strongly related to the leader's behaviour. Leaders have a deeper and more lasting influence on organizations and provide more comprehensive leadership if their focus extends beyond maintaining high standards.

2.2 Providing Incentives for Teachers

Hallinger and Murphy (1985) emphasized that an important part of the principal's role in creating a positive learning climate involves setting up a work structure that rewards and recognizes teachers for their efforts. Principals have few discretionary rewards to use with teachers. The single salary schedule and the tenure system severely limit principals' ability to motivate teachers. However, there are many forms of reward that are available to principals such as privately expressed praise, public recognition, and formal honours and awards. Meanwhile, incentive here does not mean that the principal should provide money to motivate teachers in performing their duties.

Blasé and Blasé (2000) provided a partial answer by asking teachers to describe the behaviour of principals who had a positive influence on student learning. Two broad themes emerged: talking with teachers and promoting professional development. These were expressed in specific types of behaviour such as making suggestions, giving feedback, modelling effective instruction, soliciting opinions, supporting collaboration, providing professional development opportunities, and giving praise for effective teaching. All these actions were carried out in a way that respected teacher knowledge and autonomy.

Murphy (1990, as cited in Alig-Mielcarek, 2003) state that principals foster the development of a school learning climate conducive to teaching and learning by establishing positive expectations and standards, by maintaining high visibility, providing incentives for teachers and students, and promoting professional development. This dimension deals directly with the teaching and learning process in classrooms. Meanwhile, providing incentives for teachers is one of the factors to help and develop the teaching and learning process in the classrooms

2.3 Providing Incentives for Learning

According to Noddings (1992), schools, like families, are multipurpose institutions. Although academics are the focus of schools, students need adults to care about their personal interests. To meet this need, according to Harris and Lowery (2002), the principal can be accessible to students; reward them; be an advocate for them; and provide them with a safe, secure learning environment.

It is possible to create a school learning climate, in which students' value academic achievement, by frequently rewarding and recognizing student academic achievement and improvement. In low-income schools, students need frequent, tangible rewards. The rewards need not be fancy or expensive; recognition before teachers and peers is the key. Students should have opportunities to be recognized for their achievement both within the classroom and before the school as a whole. The principal is a key factor in linking classrooms and school reward systems, ensuring that they are mutually supportive (Hallinger & Murphy, 1985).

Principals who are accessible to the students contribute to a positive climate for students. Harris and Lowery (2002) also mentioned that principals who take extra time to praise students for their achievements over the intercom, in the newspaper, or with personal notes and e-mails create a positive school climate. Principals can also use such rewards as extending lunch time, sponsoring field trips, letting students eat lunch outside, and hosting awards assemblies.

2.4 Promoting Professional Development

Freiberg (2002) stated that professional development for teachers should be built on a framework of research-based instructional strategies. These skills help teachers to bridge theory and practice and create high-quality learning environments in their classrooms. The strategies fall into three categories: organizing, instructing, and assessing. Organizing strategies include planning, lesson design, time use (time management, time on task, and pacing), advanced work, and classroom management. Ahamad & Kasim (2016) admitted that instructional strategies exist on a continuum from most teacher-centred to most student-centred: including lecture, demonstration, questioning, discussion, guided practice, independent practice, grouping, role play, simulation, and reflective inquiry. Finally, assessing strategies include student assessment and self-assessment.

According to Stallworth (1998), through site-based professional development programmes, teachers will get (i) fresh teaching ideas and management strategies; (ii) samples of successful lesson plans, and time to practise them; (iii) time to share resources and personal stories (for validation and rejuvenation); (iv) time to read useful materials on issues that directly affect their teaching and learning, such as multiculturalism; (v) time to reflect; and (vi) opportunities to reinvent.

The effect of professional development, as mentioned by Meek (1998), consists of three things: First, teachers who had taken part in any professional development programme on cooperative learning were more likely than those who had not to report using small group instruction at least once a week. Second, professional development

also paid off in teachers' use of technology in classrooms. Those who had participated in at least one formal professional development experience on the use of technology were more likely than others to report that they had used computers, video equipment, or other electronic technologies; calculators; or computers for writing. Third, teachers who had attended a professional development programme on student assessment were more likely to use portfolios than other teachers. Further, those who had taken part in professional development were more likely to include interdisciplinary problems and assessments than their counterparts who had not.

2.5 School Learning Climate and Students Achievement

Climate, literally, can be defined as the prevailing trend of public opinion or of another aspect of public life. Hoy and Miskel (1982) defined school climate as a school's personality. Brookover *et al.* (1979), Sarason (1981), Edmonds (1982) and Cohen *et al.* (2009) defined climate as the atmosphere of a school building. It is the impressions, moods and feelings one experiences when walking the corridors, sitting in the classrooms, or standing on the playground. Mc Carley, Peters & Decman (2016) stated that school climate encompasses teachers' shared perceptions of their overall work environment to include the internal features that distinguish one campus from another and its impact on the behavior of its staff members.

O'Malley, *et al.* (2015) in their study highlighted that schools were the main sources that can explain the development of academic, behavioral, social, and emotional needs of youth, regardless of their students' home situations. Findings from the study suggested that academic achievement of the students can be supported by focusing on assessing and improving students' school climate perceptions especially for youth living in higher-risk family structures.

This study was supported by the studies of Brand, *et al.* (2008) and Bear, Yang & Pasipanodya (2015) saying that school climate was associated with multiple indicators of students' academic and social-emotional development. Okorji, Igbokwe, & Ezeugbor (2016) added that school climate had a relationship with academic achievement, school attendance and school avoidance.

These job functions constitute the conceptual definitions for the headteacher variables examined in this study. These definitions will be used to help generate the specific policies, practices, and behaviour that form the questionnaires which will be used to collect data on the practice of instructional leadership among headteachers of high performing primary schools in Malaysia.

3. Objectives of the Study

The study aims to analyze the role of headteachers of excellent primary schools in promoting main dimensions of positive school climate conducive for teaching and learning. More specifically, the study aim to seek answers to the following questions.

4. Research Questions

Research Question 1: What are the practices of 'Developing and Enforcing Academic Standards' among Headteachers of High Performing Primary Schools according to headteachers' and teachers' perceptions?

Research Question 2: What are the practices of 'Providing Incentives for Teachers' among Headteachers of High Performing Primary Schools according to headteachers' and teachers' perceptions?

Research Question 3: What are the practices of 'Providing Incentives for Learning' among Headteachers of High Performing Primary Schools according to headteachers' and teachers' perceptions?

Research Question 4: What are the practices of 'Promoting Professional Development' among Headteachers of High Performing Primary Schools according to headteachers' and teachers' perceptions?

Research Question 5: What are the best practices of Positive School Learning Climate among headteachers of High Performing Primary Schools Malaysia according to headteachers' and teachers' perceptions?

5. Methodology of the Study

The Principal Instructional Management Rating Scale (PIMRS) modified by Hallinger and Murphy (1985), Latip (2006), Hatta (2010), Surayya (2016) was used as the data collection instrument through survey questionnaire. The list of high performing primary schools was acquired from the Ministry of Education Malaysia. The total respondent was 420 comprises Assistant Headteachers, Heads of Unit and Academic Teachers of different genders, ethnics, and, schools. The distribution and responses to the questionnaire from the management and teachers of high performing primary schools were really encouraging.

The analyses of responses were based on 5-Likert Scale of 1. VSD – Very Strongly Disagree; 2. SD – Strongly Disagree; 3. N – No Comment; 4. AA – Agree; 5. VSA – Very Strongly Agree. The rank and level of practices were based on scale of 1.00 – 1.99 Very Low; 2.00 – 2.99 Low; 3.00 – 3.99 High, and, 4.00 – 5.00 Very High.

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5.1 Reliability Analysis

In this study, reliability analysis was conducted to examine the Cronbach Alpha (α) for internal consistency of instruments. Figure 1 indicates the scale that was used in the study.

Figure 1: The Cronbach’s Alpha Score for Scale Used in Positive School Learning Climate

Scale Instrument/ Dimensions	Cronbach’s Alpha	No. of Items
Developing and Enforcing Academic Standards	.838	5
Providing Incentives For Teachers	.851	4
Providing Incentives for Learning	.831	4
Promoting Professional Development	.922	10

The Cronbach’s Alpha scores for scale instrument in the test range from 0.831 to 0.922 which indicate consistent scores for all variables. The value obtained in this study fulfills the recommendation of a minimum level of 0.7 Cronbach’s Alpha values for reliability (Nunnally 1978, p. 245).

6. Results of the Study

Research Question 1: What are the practices of ‘Developing and Enforcing Academic Standards’ among Headteachers of High Performing Primary Schools according to headteachers’ and teachers’ perceptions?

Table 1 presents in detail the mean, standard deviation and rank of each task involved in the practice of Developing and Enforcing Academic Standards in School Positive Learning Climate among head teachers of High Performing Primary Schools Malaysia.

Analysis of the result from the questionnaire revealed that the headteacher did promote the school learning climate by developing and enforcing academic standards. The means ranged from 4.6557 to 4.1475 and were overall very high practice with average mean 4.4754 and standard deviation 0.6475.

Table 1: Practices of ‘Developing and Enforcing Academic Standards’ among Headteachers of High Performing Primary Schools according to headteachers’ and teachers’ perceptions (N = 420)

No.	Item	Means	Standard Deviation	Rank/ Level
1.	Set high standards for the percentage of students who are expected to master important instructional objectives	4.4590	.6474	4
2.	Encourage teachers to start class on time and teach to the end of the period	4.6557	.5740	1
3.	Make known what is expected of students at different grade levels	4.5902	.5590	2
4.	Enforce a promotion standard requiring mastery of grade-level expectations	4.5246	.5658	3
5.	Support teachers when they enforce academic policies (e.g. on grading, homework, promotion, or discipline)	4.1475	.8913	5
Total - Average		4.4754	0.6475	Very High

The result of the study on Table 1 demonstrated that the best practice of ‘Developing and Enforcing Academic Standards’ was statement 2 ‘encourage teachers to start class

on time and teach to the end of the period’ was perceived as having the highest mean score 4.6557 and standard deviation 0.5740 among the five dimensions. This was followed by statement number 3 ‘make known what is expected of students at different grade levels’ with mean score 4.5902 and standard deviation 0.5590. With an almost similar mean score, statement number 4 ‘enforce a promotion standard requiring mastery of grade-level expectations’ got mean score 4.5246 and standard deviation 0.5658. Statement number 1 ‘set high standards for the percentage of students who are expected to master important instructional objectives’ came in the fourth with mean score 4.4590 and standard deviation 0.6474. Finally, statement 5 ‘support teachers when they enforce academic policies’ got the lowest mean score in this dimension with 4.1475 and standard deviation 0.8913.

Research Question 2: What are the practices of ‘Providing Incentives for Teachers’ among Headteachers of High Performing Primary Schools according to headteachers’ and teachers’ perceptions?

Table 2 presents in detail the mean, standard deviation and rank of each task involved in the practices of **Providing Incentives for Teachers** in School Positive Learning Climate among headteachers of High Performing Primary Schools Malaysia. The analysis of the study revealed that means ranged from 4.3279 to 4.1639 and were overall high practiced with total-average mean 4.2500 and standard deviation 0.8866.

Table 2: Practices of ‘Providing Incentives for Teachers’ among Headteachers of High Performing Primary Schools according to headteachers’ and teachers’ perceptions (N = 420)

No.	Item	Means	Standard Deviation	Rank/ Level
6.	Reinforce superior performance by teachers in staff meetings, newsletters, or memos	4.2787	.9332	2
7.	Compliment teachers privately for their efforts or performance	4.2295	.8830	3
8.	Acknowledge special effort or performance by teachers in memos for their personnel files	4.1639	.8598	4
9.	Reward special efforts by teachers with opportunities for professional development (e.g. new roles or in-service training)	4.3279	.8702	1
Total - Average		4.2500	0.8866	Very High

The best practice of ‘Providing Incentives for Teachers’ was statement 9 ‘rewarding special efforts by teachers with opportunities for professional development’ was perceived as having the highest mean score 4.3279 and standard deviation 0.8702 as practiced by the headteachers among the four dimensions. This was followed by statement number 6 ‘reinforcing superior performance by teachers in staff meetings, newsletters, or memos’ with mean score 4.2787 and standard deviation 0.9332. With an almost similar mean score, statement number 7 ‘complimenting teachers privately for

their efforts or performance' got mean score 4.2295 and standard deviation 0.8830 as perceived by the respondents. Statement number 8 'acknowledging special effort or performance by teachers in memos for their personnel files' came in the fourth with mean score 4.1639 and standard deviation 0.8598.

Research Question 3: What are the practices of 'Providing Incentives for Learning' among Headteachers of High Performing Primary Schools according to headteachers' and teachers' perceptions?

Table 3 presents in detail the mean, standard deviation and rank of each task involved in the practices of 'Providing Incentives for Learning' among Headteachers of High Performing Primary Schools according to headteachers' and teachers' perceptions. Analysis of the result from the questionnaire revealed that the headteacher did promote the school positive learning climate by providing incentives for learning in schools. The means ranged from 4.6721 to 4.0820 and were overall high with total-average mean 4.3729 and standard deviation 0.7165.

Table 3: Practices of 'Providing Incentives for Learning' among Headteachers of High Performing Primary Schools according to headteachers' and teachers' perceptions (N=420)

No.	Item	Means	Standard Deviation	Rank/ Level
10.	Recognize superior student achievement or improvement by seeing students in the office with their work products	4.0820	.9182	4
11.	Use assemblies to honor students for their academic work and/or behavior in class	4.6721	.5073	1
12.	Recognize students who do superior academic work with formal rewards such as an honor roll or mention in the principal's newsletter	4.5246	.6220	2
13.	Contact parents to communicate improves student performance in school	4.2131	.8188	3
Total-Average		4.3729	0.7165	Very High

Table 3 displayed that the best practice of 'Providing Incentives for Learning' was on statement 11 'use assemblies to honor students for their academic work and/or behavior in class' was perceived as having the highest mean score 4.6721 and standard deviation 0.5073 as practiced by the headteachers among the four dimensions. This was followed by statement 12 'recognizing students who do superior academic work with formal rewards such as an honor roll or mention in the principal's newsletter' with mean score 4.5246 and standard deviation 0.6220. Next was statement 13 'contact parents to communicate improves student performance in school with mean score 4.2131 and standard deviation 0.8188 as perceived by the respondents. Statement 10 'recognizing superior student achievement or improvement by seeing students in the office with their work products' came in the fourth rank with mean score 4.0820 and standard deviation 0.9182.

Research Question 4: What are the practices of ‘Promoting Professional Development’ among Headteachers of High Performing Primary Schools according to headteachers’ and teachers’ perceptions?

Table 4 displays in detail the mean, standard deviation and rank of each task involved in the practices of ‘Promoting Professional Development’ among Headteachers of High Performing Primary Schools according to headteachers’ and teachers’ perceptions.

Analysis of the result from the questionnaire revealed that the headteacher did promote the school positive learning climate by ‘Promoting Professional Development’ in schools. The means ranged from 4.5082 to 3.6393 and were overall high.

Table 4: Practices of ‘Promoting Professional Development’ among Headteachers of High Performing Primary Schools according to headteachers’ and teachers’ perceptions (N=420)

No.	Item	Means	Standard Deviation	Rank
14.	Inform teachers of opportunities for professional development	4.1639	.8977	8
15.	Select in-service activities that are consistent with the school's academic goals	4.5080	.6486	4
16.	Support teacher requests for in-service training that is directly related to the school's academic goals	4.4754	.6482	5
17.	Distribute journal articles to teachers on a regular basis	4.0000	1.0165	9
18.	Actively support the use of skills acquired during in-service training in the classroom	4.5081	.6981	3
19.	Ensure that instructional aides receive appropriate training to help students meet instructional objectives	3.6393	1.1695	10
20.	Arrange for outside speakers to make presentations on instruction at faculty meetings	4.3279	.7685	7
21.	Provide time to meet individually with teachers to discuss instructional issues	4.3607	.7753	6
22.	Sit in on teacher in-service activities concerned with instruction	4.5082	.7216	2
23.	Set aside time at faculty meetings for teachers to share ideas on instruction or information from in-service activities	4.5574	.6461	1
Total-Average		4.3049	0.7990	Very High

Table 4 indicated, statement number 23 ‘set aside time at faculty meetings for teachers to share ideas on instruction or information from in-service activities’ were perceived as having the highest mean score 4.5574 and standard deviation 0.6461. The second highest was statement number 22 ‘sit in on teacher in-service activities concerned with instruction’ mean 4.5082 and standard deviation 0.7216. The third highest was statement number 18 ‘Actively support the use of skills acquired during in-service training in the classroom’ mean 4.5081 and standard deviation 0.6981.

The fourth highest was statement number 15 ‘select in-service activities that are consistent with the school's academic goals’ with mean score 4.5080 and standard deviation 0.6486. fifth highest was statement number 16 ‘Support teacher requests for in-service training that is directly related to the school's academic goals’ mean 4.4754 and standard deviation 0.6482. Sixth highest was statement number 21 ‘provide time to meet individually with teachers to discuss instructional issues’ mean 4.3607 and standard deviation 0.7753. The seventh highest was statement number 20 ‘arrange for outside speakers to make presentations on instruction at faculty meetings’ with mean score 4.3279 and standard deviation 0.7685.

Table 4 also shows that the third lowest or rank eighth in this dimension was statement number 14 ‘inform teachers of opportunities for professional development’ with mean 4.1639 and standard deviation 0.8977. The second lowest or rank ninth was statement number 17 ‘distributing journal articles to teachers on a regular basis’ got mean score 4.000 and standard deviation 1.0165. Finally, the lowest or tenth rank was statement number 19 ‘ensure that instructional aides receive appropriate training to help students meet instructional objectives’ mean 3.6393 and standard deviation 1.1695.

Research Question 5: What are the best practices of Positive School Learning Climate among headteachers of High Performing Primary Schools Malaysia according to headteachers’ and teachers’ perceptions?

Table 5 presented the best practices of Positive School Learning Climate among headteachers of High Performing Primary Schools Malaysia according to headteachers’ and teachers’ perceptions.

Table 5: Best practices of Positive School Learning Climate among Headteachers of High Performing Primary Schools Malaysia according to headteachers’ and teachers’ perceptions (N=420)

No.	Dimensions	Means	Standard Deviation	Rank/ Level
1.	Developing and Enforcing Academic Standards	4.4754	0.6475	1 Very High
2.	Providing Incentives for Teachers	4.2500	0.8866	4 Very High
3.	Providing Incentives for Learning	4.3729	0.7165	2 Very High
4.	Promoting Professional Development	4.3049	0.7990	3 Very High
Total - Average		4.3508	0.7624	Very High

As shown on Table 5, the highest and best practice of Positive School Learning Climate among headteachers of High Performing Primary Schools Malaysia according to headteachers’ and teachers’ perceptions was dimension 1 ‘Developing and Enforcing

Academic Standards' mean 4.4754 and standard deviation 0.6475 with very high level of practiced. The second highest was on dimension 3 'Providing Incentives for Learning' with mean 4.3729 and standard deviation 0.7165 with very high practiced. The third was dimension 'Promoting Professional Development' mean 4.3049 and standard deviation 0.7990 with very high practiced. The fourth was dimension 'Providing Incentives for Teachers' mean 4.2500 and standard deviation 0.8866 with very high practiced.

It is interesting to observe that all dimensions achieved very high level of practiced of Positive School Learning Climate among headteachers of High Performing Primary Schools Malaysia according to headteachers' and teachers' perceptions of total 420 respondents. The Total – Average for Positive School Learning Climate was mean 4.3508 and standard deviation 0.7624.

7. Summary & Discussion

7.1 What are the relationship between Best Practices of Promoting a Positive School Learning Climate among Headteacher of High Performing Primary Schools and Education Blueprint 2013-2025 Malaysia?

It is amazing to observe that all dimensions achieved very high level of practiced of School Positive Learning Climate among headteachers of High Performing Primary Schools Malaysia according to headteachers' and teachers' perceptions with mean 4.3661 and standard deviation 1.7729.

The 'Very High' practice of dimension 'Developing and Enforcing Academic Standards' was significant to the realization of 'System Aspiration' stipulated in the Education Blueprint 2013 – 2025. There are five outcomes that this Blueprint aspires to for the Malaysian education system as a whole namely access, quality, equity, unity, and efficiency. The 'Very High' practice of excellent primary schools' Headteachers on statement 'Set high standards for the percentage of students who are expected to master important instructional objectives' mean 4.4590 and standard deviation 0.6474 was significant to realize the Blueprint 'quality' aspiration of 'All children will have the opportunity to attain an excellent education that is uniquely Malaysian and comparable to the best international systems'.

Another 'Very High' practice of excellent primary schools' headteachers on statement 'Make known what is expected of students at different grade levels' mean 4.5902 was prominently congruent to the Blueprint 'equity' aspiration of 'Top-performing school systems deliver the best possible education for every child, regardless of geography, gender, or socioeconomic background. The Ministry aspires to halve the current urban-rural, socio-economic, and gender achievement gaps by 2020'.

The headteachers of excellent primary schools 'Very High' practice on statement 'Encourage teachers to start class on time and teach to the end of the period' mean 4.6557 really significant to achieve the Blueprint 'unity' aspiration 'As students spend over a quarter of their time in school from the ages of 7 to 17, schools are in a key position to foster unity. Through interacting with individuals from a range of

socioeconomic, religious, and ethnic backgrounds—and learning to understand, accept and embrace differences—a shared set of experiences and aspirations for Malaysia's future can be built. The Ministry aspires to create a system where students have opportunities to build these shared experiences and aspirations that form the foundation for unity'.

The Best Practice of Providing Incentives for Learning among Headteachers of High Performing Primary Schools Malaysia according to the Principals and Teachers Perceptions achieved mean 4.3729. This 'Very High' level practice of headteachers might become significant factor to realize the Blueprint Student Aspirations that beyond these system-wide outcomes, stakeholders were also very clear on what 'quality' should be at the individual level. In a nutshell, educators, parents, students, and other members of the public were united in a vision of education as a vehicle for the holistic development of children—intellectually, spiritually, emotionally, and physically. This is the same vision that has underscored all education improvement efforts since the National Education Philosophy for Malaysia was written in 1988. (Mohamad Johdi, 2014).

Looking ahead, the Blueprint will continue to use the National Education Philosophy's vision of a balanced education as its foundation for individual student aspirations. It has also drawn on learning from other high-performing systems to develop a refined articulation of the specific skills and attributes that students would need to thrive in tomorrow's economy and globalised world. (Ministry of Education, Malaysia, 2012).

The above dimension was supported by the headteachers' 'Very High' practiced on statement 'Recognize students who do superior academic work with formal rewards such as an honor roll or mention in the principal's newsletter' mean 4.45246. Another contribution of the realization was headteachers' 'Very High' practices on statement 'Use assemblies to honor students for their academic work and/or behavior in class' mean 4.6721. Consequently, both items are significant to the Blueprint Student Aspiration on 'access' that 'Every child in Malaysia deserves equal access to an education that will enable that child to achieve his or her potential. The Ministry thus aspires to ensure universal access and full enrolment of all children from preschool through to upper secondary school level Form 5 by year 2020.

The study suggested that the very high practice of headteachers of excellent primary schools are significant factor to realize the Blueprint Student aspiration in Knowledge, Thinking Skills, Leadership skills, Bilingual Proficiency, Ethics and Spirituality, and, National identity. The findings were prominently relevant and significant to realize the Ministry of Education 11 shifts which require the most urgent attention. Some of these shifts represent a change in strategy, direction and represent a move away from current practices. (Ministry of Education, Malaysia, 2012).

Cooperatively, these aspirations and shifts address every stakeholder and the main concerns of the public. The Ministry hopes that this inclusiveness will provide the basis for a common focus that can be embraced by all Malaysians towards producing

first class human capital and high-developed Malaysia in 2025 via Education Blueprint 2013-2025.

8. Conclusion

In fact, the most important and the most difficult job of promoting School Positive Learning Climate of instructional leader is to change the prevailing culture of a school. A school's culture has far more influence on life and learning in the schoolhouse than the president of the country, the state department of education, the superintendent, the school board, or even the principal, teachers, and parents can ever have. One cannot, of course, change a school culture alone. But one can provide forms of leadership that invite others to join as observers of the old and architects of the new. Meanwhile, the principal must ensure all the elements within school, especially something which challenges the teaching and learning process.

It is hoped that this study provides useful findings which will effectively assist the process of promoting a positive school learning climate among headteachers and teachers of primary schools in Malaysia. Consequently, facilitate and improve students' academic performance in achieving the first class human capital compatibly excellent nationally and internationally as stipulated in National Philosophy of Education, Vision 2020 and aspiration of the Malaysia Education Development Plan 2013-2025.

References

1. Abdullah, Y.A., (2001). *The Holy Quran*. United Kingdom: Wordworth Editions Ltd.
2. Ahamad, Z., & Kasim, A. L. (2016). Organizational Climate as an editor of the relationship between Transformational Leadership and Innovative Behavior in school. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Education*,4(04). p5168-5176.
3. Allen, N., Grigsby, B., & Peters, M. L. (2015). Does Leadership Matter? Examining the relationship among Transformational Leadership, School Climate, and Student achievement. *International Journal of Educational Leadership Preparation*, 10(2), 1-22.
4. Bandyopadhyay, S., Cornell, D., & Konold, T. (2009). Validity of three school climate scales to assess bullying, aggressive attitudes, and help seeking. *School Psychology Review*, 38(3), 338-335.
5. Bear, G. G., Gaskins, C., Blank, J., & Chen, F. F. (2011). Delaware school climate survey-Student: Its factor structure, concurrent validity, and reliability. *Journal of School Psychology*, 49, 157-174.
6. Bear, G. G., Yang, C., & Pasipanodya, E. (2015). Assessing School Climate Validation of a Brief Measure of the Perceptions of Parents. *Journal of psych educational assessment*, 33(2), 115-129.

7. Brand, S., Felner, R. D., Seitsinger, A., Burns, A., & Bolton, N. (2008). A large scale study of the assessment of the social environment of middle and secondary schools: The validity and utility of teachers' ratings of school climate, cultural pluralism, and safety problems for understanding school effects and school improvement. *Journal of School Psychology, 46*, 507-535.
8. Brand, S., Felner, R. D., Shim, M., Seitsinger, A., & Dumas, T. (2003). Middle school improvement and reform: Development and validation of a school-level assessment of climate, cultural pluralism, and school safety. *Journal of Educational Psychology, 95*, 570-588.
9. Gottfredson, G. D., Gottfredson, D. C., Payne, A. A., & Gottfredson, N. C. (2005). School climate predictors of school disorder: Results from a national study of delinquency prevention in schools. *Journal of Research in Crime & Delinquency, 42*, 412-444.
10. Hallinger, P., & Heck, R. (1996). Reassessing the principal's role in school effectiveness: A review of empirical research, 1980-1995. *Educational Administration Quarterly, 32*(1), 5-44.
11. Helen M. M. & Susan M. P. (2003). Principals' leadership and schools' performance: an integration of transformational and instructional leadership. *Educational Administration Quarterly, 39*, (3), 370-397.
12. Houtte, M., V. (2005) Climate or culture? a plea for conceptual clarity in school effectiveness research. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement, 16* (1), 71 – 89.
13. Latif, Mohamad (2010) Principals Practice of Instructional Leadership at Secondary Schools Malaysia. PhD Thesis (Unpublished). Bangi: Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia.
14. Leithwood, k., Jantzi, D. and Steinbach, R. (1999) *Changing Leadership for Changing Times*, Buckingham: Open University Press.
15. Loukas, A., Suzuki, R., & Horton, K. D. (2006). Examining school connectedness as a mediator of school climate effects. *Journal of Research on Adolescence, 16*, 491-501.
16. Mc Carley, T. A., Peters, M. L., & Decman, J. M. (2016). Transformational leadership related to school climate a multi-level analysis. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership, 44*(2), 322-342.
17. O'Malley, M., Voight, A., Renshaw, T. L., & Eklund, K. (2015). School climate, family structure, and academic achievement: A study of moderation effects. *School Psychology Quarterly, 30*(1), 142.
18. Okorji, P. N., Igbokwe, I. C., & Ezeugbor, C. O. (2016). Relationship between school climate and principals' job performance in secondary schools. *European Scientific Journal, 12*(4). P55
19. Southworth, G. (2002). Instructional leadership in schools' development: Reflections from research. *School Organization, 12*(2), 73-92.
20. Surayya Abu Bakar. (2016). Practices of Positive School Learning Climate among Headteachers of High Performing Primary Schools in Malaysia. MEd Dissertation (Unpublished). Gombak: IIUM.

21. Tajasom, A., Zainal, A., A. (2011) Principals' leadership style and school climate: teachers ' perspectives from principals' leadership style and school climate: teachers' perspectives from Malaysia. *The International Journal of Leadership in Public Services*. 7 (4), 314-333.

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